

CORRUPTION AND SWOT UP OF IT'S MECHANISM

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Abstract:

Corruption is operationally defined as the misuse of entrusted power for private gain. Transparency International further differentiates between “according to rule” corruption & “against the rule” corruption. Facilitation payments, where a bribe is paid to receive preferential treatment. What is corruption for something that the bribe receiver is required to do by law, constitute the former. The latter, on the other hand is a bribe paid to obtain services the bribe receiver is prohibited from providing.

Introduction

Corruption literally means to destroy (from the Latin corrumpo); is not a rare phenomenon; takes many forms with different types of participants, settings, stakes, techniques & different degrees of cultural legitimacy is not only about stealing: it can also relate to the abuse of power in decision-making processes. It is a form of behavior that deviates from ethics, morality, tradition, law & civic virtue.

Definition of Corruption:

The term “corruption” is used as a shorthand reference for a large range of illicit or illegal activities. Although there is no universal or comprehensive definition as to what constitutes corrupt behavior, the most prominent definitions share a common emphasis upon the abuse of public power or position for personal advantage.

The Oxford Unabridged Dictionary defines corruption as “perversion or destruction of integrity in the discharge of public duties by bribery or favor”.

The Merriam Webster’s Collegiate Dictionary defines it as “inducement to wrong by improper or unlawful means (as bribery)”.

The succinct definition utilized by the World Bank is “the abuse of public office for private gain”.

This definition is similar to that employed by Transparency International (TI) the leading NGO in the global anti-corruption effort:

Corruption:

- Dishonest or fraudulent conduct by those in power, typically.
- The action of making someone or something morally depraved or the state of being so.

The Webster dictionary defines corruption as, “to corrupt is to change from good to bad.” Therefore we can argue that it is to be morally debased. It is a pervasion of morality as well as integrity.

Further definition states that corruption is, “it is an inducement by means of improper considerations to commit a violation of duty”.

Components of Corruption:

The following are common components of corruption:

1. Agent/principal relationship:

“Which is related to an agent improperly benefiting from activities relating to handling of his principal’s mandate, e.g. abuse of government property, equipment, and labour by public officials?

2. *Bribery:*

“Which refers to consideration, giving an inducement to influence conduct in one’s favour, contrary to standing procedures and regulatio

3. *Fraud:*

Which is a misrepresentation done to obtain unfair advantage by giving or receiving false advantageous information?

4. *Nepotism:*

Which entails showing special favors to one's relatives as against other competitors in securing of contracts, services and employment.

5. *Extortion:*

Which is the unlawful extraction of money or favour by force or intimidation?

6. *Embezzlement:*

Which is the illegal diversion of principal’s goods to one’s own use?

7. *Money laundering:*

Which involves the depositing and transferring of money and other proceeds of illegal activities? It is an act of legitimizing proceeds of illegal activities.

8. *Abuse of public property:*

Which tends to be more prevalent where there is no citizen’s oversight facilities and where there is obvious monopoly of power by public officials, which is exercised with impunity. Public labour can be diverted to individual use while public properties get hired out for private gain. This is more common with respect to services offered freely or at subsidized rates by the state and its subsidiaries where such services are either scarce or beyond the reach of the majority of the people.

9. *Gifts for services which do not need an explicit quid pro quo:*

If however, the individual gifts are large enough to have even a marginal impact on the recipient's behavior or quid pro quo is implicit, this calls for procedures and regulations to be put in place to govern the offering and receiving of such gifts.

10. *Inside trading:*

Which involves the use of information secured during the course of duty as an agent for personal gain? The information is then leaked to companies competing for tender as well as on the stock exchange giving the party with such information an unfair advantage over other competitors.

11. *Plundering of state resources:*

It is an increasing phenomenon where people even go to war for control of resources for purposes of plundering proceeds and laundering them for personal gain.

This is the case in the wars of Angola, Sierra-Leone and the Democratic Republic of Congo to mention only a few.

12. *Under Invoicing/Double Invoicing:*

This is a prevalent form of corruption in the Private sector and aims at avoiding paying duty and taxes. Production of invoices and money earned is under-declared with the connivance of the buyer while double invoicing relates to issuing multiple invoices for purposes of misleading public authorities for private gain.

13. *Patronage:*

It is a system of governance, where rewards are offered for loyalty.

14. *Speed money:*

It is paid to quicken processes caused by bureaucratic delays and shortage of resources. It normally occurs in offices where. Licenses, permits, inspection certificates and clearance

documents are processed. Over regulation and laborious and endless paperwork, will encourage the rich and powerful to try and circumvent tedious processes and procedures, thus entice officials to take bribes.

Most of these components of corruption are prohibited in the penal codes of many countries, which is why many people now identify corruption with crime and not with sustainable development.

The Nature of Corruption:

Corruption manifests itself differently according to the type of government, level of democracy, economic development and magnitude of the corrupt. In analyzing corruption, Emphasis is generally placed on the different levels of corruption depending on type and magnitude. The two types commonly identified

- a) Petty corruption and
- b) Grand corruption.

This also affects the type of intervention strategies that governments employ to curb corruption.

a) Petty corruption:

This type of corruption is also called routine or bureaucratic corruption. In some developing countries, civil servants do not earn adequate money and they tend to augment their salaries through corruption. Police, customs, immigration and

Offices responsible for issuing licenses tend to augment their salaries by demanding money for coke, etc. Petty corruption relates to tips, commissions or kickbacks that are usually demanded by junior officials in the public sector from the public for official services to be rendered. Petty corruption tends to be visible and irritating to the public. The money involved is not much, but the total amount can add to billions of dollars. This type of corruption is also called routine or bureaucratic Corruption. It is easy to stop through entrapments, so it is a target of many prevention programmes.

b) Grand corruption:

Grand corruption on the other hand, often involves prominent persons in both the private and public sectors who exercise influence over large government contracts. Large sums of money and other remunerations are involved for decisions made in one's favour. It has been argued that grand corruption has a more negative impact on the economy than petty corruption and thrives where there are discretionary powers and unchecked authority of senior bureaucrats without corresponding transparency and accountability. Grand corruption can be difficult to detect as it may take place in the guise of legality thus making it less visible to the ordinary person until a crisis occurs or after its exposure.

References

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